

1 **Investigations on single and multi-grain optically stimulated luminescence**
2 **(OSL) sensitivity and electron spin resonance (ESR) signals in quartz**
3 **derived from sandstones: Insights on provenance of quartz in ancient**
4 **depositional systems**

5

6 Aditi K. Dave¹, Daniela Constantin¹, Relu D. Roban², Mihai N. Ducea^{2,3}, Cristian Panaiotu²,
7 Alida Timar-Gabor^{1,4}

8 ¹Institute for Interdisciplinary Research in Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-
9 Napoca, Romania

10 ²Faculty of Geology and Geophysics, University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

11 ³Department of Geosciences, University of Arizona, Tucson, Arizona, USA

12 ⁴Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca,
13 Romania

14

15 **Keywords:** Single-grain luminescence sensitivity, Optically Stimulated luminescence (OSL),
16 Electron spin resonance (ESR), Quartz, E₁ centre, Al-hole centres, provenance, sediment-
17 routing, sandstones

18

19 **Abstract:**

20 Trapped charge techniques of luminescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) are classic tools
21 for dating Quaternary deposits. Over the past decade, these techniques have been routinely
22 applied to investigate provenance and /or the sedimentary history of grains based on the different
23 luminescence and ESR characteristics of quartz. Of these, optically stimulated luminescence
24 (OSL) sensitivity is one of the most widely investigated parameter for luminescence-based
25 provenance approach. A majority of studies on this parameter are based on evaluation of multi-
26 grain OSL sensitivity of the samples. This is particularly concerning because single-grain quartz
27 luminescence studies have shown that the luminescence signal of a multi-grain aliquot is
28 contributed by less than ~1-10% of the total grains. Since the sole criteria for discrimination of
29 sources based on luminescence sensitivity relies on its intensity, therefore the results based on
30 multi-grain analysis will most likely be skewed depending on the proportion and ‘brightness’ of

31 a few grains. This demands a need to evaluate the potential of single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity
32 in provenance studies. In this study, we investigate single and multi-grain quartz OSL
33 sensitivities from compositionally different sandstones with well-characterised sources based on
34 U-Pb zircon ages. We further complement this analysis with characterisation of ESR centres
35 commonly used in quartz provenance, namely E'_{1} and $[AlO_4]^0$ centres. Our study shows that
36 single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity can help distinguish between sediments that have a
37 predominant input from a single source as compared to those with contribution from multiple
38 sources, which otherwise cannot be inferred from multi-grain studies. Moreover, our results on
39 characterisation of quartz-based ESR intensity of E'_{1} and saturated $[AlO_4]^0$ centres successfully
40 differentiates between sandstones and further complements the luminescence-based
41 characterisation.

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44

45 Identifying source and transport history of sediments is key to reconstructing sediment routing
46 in sedimentary systems, and consequently reflects the role of climate and tectonics on earth
47 surface processes and landforms. Provenance analysis in sedimentary environments is
48 conventionally associated with identifying and linking source areas to their ultimate
49 depositional sink. While the concept of tracking the journey of sediment grains from source
50 to sink - through cycles of erosion, burial and transport - is a rather recent addition to
51 provenance analysis, but it certainly leads to a more integrated and comprehensive approach
52 to understanding sedimentary provenance (Allen, 2008). In recent years, trapped charge dating
53 techniques of luminescence, especially optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and electron
54 spin resonance (ESR) are being widely explored as promising tools for determining the
55 provenance as well as the sedimentary history of quartz from various sedimentary settings,
56 ranging from modern to ancient depositional environments (Sawakuchi et al., 2011, 2018;
57 Jeong and Choi., 2012; Shimada et al., 2013; Toyoda et al., 2016; del Río et al., 2021; Mineli
58 et al., 2021; Dave et al., 2022a,b). Unlike other methods in quartz provenance analysis such
59 as trace elements in quartz (Ackerson et al., 2015), luminescence and ESR signals in quartz
60 exhibit dynamic behaviour and thus have the potential to not only discriminate between
61 different source rocks, but also gain insight on the sedimentary history of the quartz grain.

62

63 Although in its nascent stages of development, luminescence sensitivity of quartz,
64 conventionally defined as luminescence emitted in response to a given dose per unit mass, has
65 been linked to both - its source area and sedimentary history (Sawakuchi et al., 2011, 2018;
66 Dave et al., 2022b; Alexanderson, 2022; Capaldi et al., 2023) and therefore, has the potential
67 to reflect one or both of these factors to varying degrees within a sedimentary depositional
68 record. One of the main challenges in sedimentary provenance analysis is that sediments are
69 composed of grains that are transported in variable amounts from different sources (Basu,
70 1985; Weltje and von Eynatten, 2004). In terms of luminescence sensitivity, this implies that
71 quantitative bulk-methods of provenance analysis can often represent either the dominant
72 source or the source with a 'stronger signature' in the sediment, while input from smaller
73 contributing sources or those from sources with a 'weaker signature' is often lost. Majority of
74 the studies on provenance analysis based on luminescence sensitivity are performed on multi-
75 grain quartz aliquots (e.g. del Río et al., 2021; Bartyik et al., 2021; Souza et al., 2023). It is
76 well known that in multi-grain analysis the bulk luminescence characteristics are dictated by
77 less than ~1-10% of the total grains (Duller et al., 2000; Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018). This
78 implies that multi-grain luminescence sensitivity infers results based on a few grains that
79 dominate the signal, consequently skewing provenance interpretations. Therefore, there is a
80 need to investigate luminescence sensitivity at a single-grain level, to better understand to
81 what extent luminescence sensitivity of individual quartz grains reflect different source
82 contributions within the sediment.

83
84 In addition to luminescence-based provenance approach, a few ESR centres in quartz have
85 also been investigated as potential indicators for provenance. Of these, the E'₁ centre
86 comprising of an unpaired electron in an oxygen vacancy ($\equiv\text{Si}\cdot$, Feigl et al., 1974) is the most
87 investigated ESR centre in quartz for provenance studies (Nagashima et al., 2007; Toyoda et
88 al., 2016; Dave et al., 2022a). Most studies, either use heat-treated E'₁ centre (i.e., the intensity
89 of E'₁ centre after heating to 350°C; Toyoda et al., 2016) or natural E'₁ centre (Dave et al.,
90 2022a) for characterisation of quartz. Both these centres are believed to be characteristic of
91 the source rock from which they are derived and have been successfully applied to
92 differentiate between sediments derived from different source rocks (e.g., Nagashima et al.,
93 2007, 2011; Dave et al., 2022a; Timar-Gabor et al., 2023). Other ESR centres like the residual
94 $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ centre, i.e., the non-bleachable $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ centre that remains in quartz even after
95 exposure to light, has also been used to discriminate between sediments from different sources
96 (Tissoux et al., 2012, 2015). Until now all provenance-based investigations on ESR centres in

97 quartz have been performed on bulk (multi-grain) quartz. The study of ESR centres on
98 individual quartz grains has been attempted previously for application in dating studies
99 (Beerten et al, 2003). However, practical application of ESR measurements on single-grain
100 quartz can be time consuming due to the use of comparatively more sensitive Q-Band ESR
101 spectroscopy, which provides higher spectral resolution for the ESR signals but lowers the
102 inherent precision of the measurements as compared to commonly used X-Band ESR
103 spectroscopy. This can result in repeated measurements for a sample. This aspect will
104 particularly affect provenance studies, wherein repeated measurements will have to be
105 conducted on hundreds of single grains of quartz in order to get a representative result for an
106 individual sample.

107
108 In this study, we examine single and multi-grain quartz OSL sensitivity as well as investigate
109 ESR centres in quartz extracted from three compositionally different sandstones from Outer
110 Carpathian Orogen and Eastern European Platform (Figure 1). We choose to conduct our
111 analyses on these sandstones for two main reasons: *First*, the ease of extraction of quartz from
112 sedimentary rocks unlike igneous and metamorphic rocks (Guralnik et al., 2015). *Second*, the
113 availability of U-Pb zircon ages, well-known depositional ages as well as well-characterised
114 sediment-routing systems for these deposits, which provides a robust natural testing ground
115 to investigate geological controls on characteristics of luminescence and ESR-centres in
116 quartz. Comparison of luminescence sensitivity of single grain versus multi-grain quartz gives
117 an insight into how and to what extent variability in sensitivity of individual grains dictate the
118 behaviour of bulk (or multi-grain) luminescence sensitivity. We further supplement these
119 studies with investigation of different ESR centres in bulk quartz that are commonly used in
120 provenance studies, such as the E_1' and $[AlO_4]^0$ centre (hereon referred to as Al-hole centre).
121 Such a combined trapped charge approach allows us to assess the potential scope as well as
122 limitations of their application in provenance studies.

123

124 **2. Study Region**

125

126 In this study, we investigate sandstones from three compositionally different sedimentary settings
127 in Eastern Europe: the Oligocene-Miocene sedimentary deposits of the Fusaru and Kliwa
128 formations in the fold and thrust belt of the East Carpathians, which represents the main structure
129 marking continental collision between mobile Europe and stable cratonic Eastern Europe, and

130 the Neoproterozoic Yampil Member of the Mohyliv Formation from East European Platform,
131 Republic of Moldova. The Kliwa and Fusaru sedimentary rocks are part of two compositionally
132 different turbidite fan systems that occur on opposite margins of the Moldavides foreland Basin
133 in the Eastern Carpathians (Figure 1) – they crop out along a strike for over 150 km. A
134 palaeogeographical reconstruction of the Oligocene turbidite fan system of the Fusaru and Kliwa
135 depositional system modified from Roban et al (2023) is provided in the supplementary
136 information (Figure S1).

137 *Fusaru*. The Fusaru deposits dominate the internal western active flank of the Moldavides
138 foreland basin. They consist of medium to coarse-grain sandstones, that are texturally immature
139 with poor grain size sorting and sub-angular to subrounded grains; with a matrix that is
140 predominantly composed of clay minerals. According to U-Pb ages of detrital zircons, the
141 maximum depositional age for the youngest part of the Fusaru Formation is 22.22 ± 0.20 Ma
142 (Roban et al., 2023). The U-Pb age distributions (Figure 2a), on detrital zircons from Fusaru
143 sandstones (Roban et al., 2023) suggest that the sediments were sourced from the internal uplifted
144 Getic and Bucovinian thrust sheets and the cretaceous accretionary wedge of the Carpathians.
145 This can also be seen from the dominance of metamorphic lithoclasts (i.e., gneiss fragments and
146 schists) similar to the metamorphic basement of Getic and Bucovinian Nappes. Thus, the textural
147 and compositional immaturity of the Fusaru sandstones, coupled with the Carpathian
148 provenance, suggests a short routing system of c. 50-100 Km (Roban et al., 2023).

149 *Kliwa*. The Kliwa deposits are located along the eastern passive margin of the Moldavides
150 foreland Basin. These sandstones are quartz-rich and have high textural maturity, with
151 comparatively better sorting and more rounded grains, and the matrix predominately consists of
152 silica and carbonate, unlike Fusaru sandstones. Palaeontological evidence based on calcareous
153 nannofossil records (Melinte, 2005; Ștefănescu et al., 2018; Roban et al., 2023) suggests that the
154 Lower Kliwa Formation was active during Late Rupelian-early Chattian (c. 30-23 Mya), while
155 the depositional age of the Upper Kliwa Formation is estimated to be Aquitanian to early
156 Burdigalian in age (c.22-19 Ma). U-Pb zircon age distribution on Lower Kliwa sandstones, varies
157 from 114-3000 Ma (Roban et al., 2023; Figure 2a) suggesting that the Eastern European
158 Platform/Craton was a major sediment source with minor inputs from the southern units of the
159 Moesian Platform, North Dobrogea and the Balkan orogen. Răbăgia et al (2011) suggested that
160 the Upper Kliwa Formation deposits were recycled from the deformed Lower Kliwa deposits
161 during the Lower Miocene. For this reason, we expect the U-Pb zircon age distribution to be
162 similar to that of Lower Kliwa Formation (Roban et al., 2023). Overall, the sedimentological

163 and petrological analysis combined with provenance analysis on Kliwa suggests sediment
164 routing through long river systems (> 400 Km) with considerable scope for multiple stages of
165 sediment recycling (Roban et al., 2023).

166 *Yampil*. The Yampil sandstone are located in the Moldova-Podillya-Volyn foreland basin
167 (Francovschi et al., 2023), situated on the southwest margin of the Baltica Continent (East
168 European Platform). The depositional age of Yampil sedimentary beds was estimated to be more
169 than 560 Ma based on U-Pb zircon ages on the overlying ash beds (Soldatenko et al., 2019),
170 which is also reaffirmed by the Ediacaran fossil biota found in the siliciclastic rocks of the
171 Mohliv-Podilskyi group. In the Cosăuți stone quarry (the sampling site in this study), the Yampil
172 deposits discordantly overlies the Rapakiwi-type granite of the Ukrainian Shield. These granites
173 have an age of c. 2000 Ma (Paszkowski et al., 2019; Ion Francovschi personal communication)
174 which correlates with the age of the detrital zircons extracted from the Yampil sandstone (Roban
175 et al., 2020), thus supporting the idea of proximity of the source area to the Ediacaran Yampil
176 sedimentary deposits. In addition, these deposits consist of fine to very coarse sandstones, with
177 a high proportion of unstable feldspar fragments, indicating a short and quick transport pathway.

178

179 **3. Material and Methods**

180 **3.1. Samples**

181 In this study we collected five sandstones from three compositionally different depositional
182 systems in Romania and the Republic of Moldova. A brief description of the sedimentary rocks
183 is given below. The sampling locations are shown in the map in Figure 1 and sampling-sites for
184 these sandstones are shown in Figure S2 in the supplementary.

185 **F-01** (45°30' 15.80" N, 26°14'35.6" E) is a coarse-grained sandstone, collected from an exposed
186 outcrop of the Fusaru Formation near the artificially dammed Lake Siriu in the Buzău River
187 valley. This sample corresponds to sample FS0 analysed by Roban et al (2023) for U-Pb ages on
188 detrital zircons.

189 **K-01** (45°21' 31.29" N, 26°19'57.2" E) is an uncohesive fine-grained sandstone and belongs to
190 the Upper Kliwa Formation. It was collected from a c. 100 m thick sedimentary outcrop, south
191 of the village of Chirleşti in the Buzău River valley.

192 **K-02** (45°23' 4.46" N, 26°19'28.63" E) and **K-03** (45°23' 1.12" N, 26°23'24.68" E) are
193 uncohesive fine-grained sandstones that belong to the Lower Kliwa Formation. K-02 was
194 collected from exposed outcrops at the banks of the Buzău River, c. 2 Km north of the village of
195 Mlăjet. This outcrop was identified as levee deposits of the Kliwa turbiditic fan system. Sample
196 K-03 was collected from a c. 100 m thick sedimentary outcrop located c. 1 Km south of the
197 village of Colții de Jos. Sample K-02 corresponds to sample KS0 analysed by Roban et al (2023)
198 for U-Pb ages on detrital zircons.

199 **N5** (48°14' 09" N, 28°18'20.3" E) is a coarse-grained sandstone collected from an exposed
200 outcrop from a quarry located close to the village of Cosăuți on the Dneister River in the Republic
201 of Moldova. U-Pb ages on detrital zircons were previously analysed for this sample by Roban et
202 al (2020).

203

204 **3.2. Methods and measurement protocols**

205 All five sandstone samples were processed in subdued red-light conditions to extract coarse
206 grained (250-500 μm) quartz using standard luminescence dating protocols. A detailed account
207 of sample preparation and instrumentation for luminescence and ESR measurements are given
208 in the supplementary. In this study, we performed optically stimulated luminescence (OSL)
209 sensitivity measurements on single and multi-grain quartz as well as ESR measurements on bulk
210 quartz from all five sandstone samples.

211

212 *3.2.1. Single grain OSL sensitivity*

213 Single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity measurements were conducted on 29 single-grain aluminium
214 discs for each sample. Each single-grain aluminium disc consists of a 10 x 10 grid of 100 holes,
215 each with a depth and diameter of 300 μm ; that was loaded with quartz grains under a microscope
216 to ensure maximum occupancy of the holes with grains. It must be noted that, the diameter of
217 the holes on the single grain disc (300 μm) are very close to the lower limit of the grain size used
218 in this study (250-500 μm). This results in a luminescence sensitivity distribution that represents
219 a narrow grain size range, but it ensures that only one grain occupies a hole in a single grain disc
220 and therefore the luminescence signal intensity arises from a single grain only. The grain-sizes
221 of three representative samples (N5, K-02 and F-01) are illustrated in more detail using scanning
222 electron microscope (SEM) imaging in Figure S3 in the supplementary.

223

224 The OSL sensitivity measurements were estimated as part of a single aliquot regeneration
225 protocol (SAR; Murray and Wintle, 2000, 2003), which is outlined in Table S1 of the
226 supplementary. The OSL luminescence sensitivity from each grain was evaluated in response to
227 34 Gy from the first 0.1s of the OSL decay signal after a subtraction of background signal
228 averaged over the last 0.4s. As per convention, luminescence sensitivity is expressed as photon
229 counts per unit dose per unit mass (cts/Gy·mg) of the sample. However, in this case due to the
230 low luminescence sensitivity of individual quartz grains in response to a unit dose, we express
231 luminescence sensitivity of our sample as counts per 34 Gy per grain (cts/34 Gy·grain) in order
232 to achieve meaningful counting statistics. The single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity distribution of
233 each sample is represented as a histogram with a bin size of 100 cts as shown in Figure 2.

234
235 One of the challenges that arise with analysis of OSL sensitivity of individual grains of quartz
236 with very low luminescence emission is the inability to differentiate background noise from the
237 low photon counts emitted from individual grains. For this purpose, we evaluate a detection
238 threshold for luminescence sensitivity of individual grains by measuring luminescence
239 sensitivity (photon counts per 0.1s) for two single-grain discs that are (i) empty and (ii) loaded
240 with sample (N5) that is bleached with blue diodes for 100s. The protocol for analysis of the
241 detection threshold is presented in Table S2. The photon count distribution (cts/0.1s) from the
242 analysis of empty single-grain discs and that with bleached grains are shown in Figure S4. Based
243 on the results from these experiments, we estimate the detection threshold for single-grain quartz
244 OSL sensitivity for our luminescence reader and samples to be 22 counts in the first 0.1s.

245

246 3.2.2. Multi-grain OSL sensitivity

247 For multi-grain quartz OSL sensitivity investigations, we investigate our samples using a two-
248 fold approach:

249

250 *Treating a single-grain disc as a multi-grain aliquot - 'Pseudo multi-grain luminescence*
251 *sensitivity' analysis.* In this analysis, we treat each single-grain disc as a multi-grain aliquot by
252 summing the luminescence of all grains on the disc. Such an analysis provides a (i) 'controlled'
253 setup – since each disc comprises of not more than 100 grains, and (ii) an 'unbiased' (real)
254 approach – since the likelihood of 'how many' or 'which' (dim or bright) grain ends up on a disc
255 is random. Such a 'pseudo multi-grain' OSL sensitivity analysis can help visualise how
256 dispersion in OSL sensitivity of individual grains control the overall multi-grain (bulk)

257 sensitivity. In this analysis, we analysed 29 pseudo multigrain aliquots, and accepted only those
258 aliquots (see Figure. 3a,b) which yielded a dose response curve that fit a single saturating
259 exponential or the sum of two exponentials, with 10% recycling and 5% recuperation for each
260 aliquot.

261
262 *Conventional multi-grain (single aliquot) luminescence sensitivity analysis.* Here we conduct
263 luminescence sensitivity measurements on 9 multi-grain aliquots for each sample. Each multi-
264 grain aliquot consist of a ~9.5 mm monolayer of quartz grains that are adhered to a stainless steel
265 disc using silicon oil. The OSL sensitivity measurements were performed as part of a SAR
266 protocol (Murray and Wintle, 2000, 2003) as shown in Table S1 and the resulting dose response
267 curves reconstructed from these measurements are presented in Figure 3. The OSL luminescence
268 sensitivity from each aliquot was evaluated in response to 34 Gy from the first ~0.8s of the OSL
269 decay signal after a subtraction of background signal averaged over the last 8s. We normalise the
270 OSL sensitivity of each aliquot to its mass and the resulting average OSL sensitivity of each
271 sample is represented as counts per 34 Gy per unit mass (cts/34 Gy·mg).

272
273 *Note.* For consistency we estimate the OSL sensitivity in all cases in response to 34 Gy. It must
274 be noted that results from single-grain and multigrain aliquots are not directly comparable as
275 they are performed on different readers and with different light sources (green laser versus blue
276 diodes respectively). However, a comparison of the interpretation derived from single and multi-
277 grain OSL sensitivity results can give us an insight on the advantages of the former over the
278 latter.

279
280 *3.2.3. Electron Spin Resonance measurements*

281 ESR investigations were performed on an X-Band Bruker EMX Plus spectrometer. In this study
282 we measured the intensity of two paramagnetic centres in quartz from all samples, namely E'₁,
283 and Al-hole centre. We performed these measurements for all samples under two conditions: (i)
284 natural conditions, i.e., measurements were performed on quartz extracted from samples as it is,
285 and (ii) after bleaching in the laboratory for 75 days. A detailed account of ESR measurement
286 parameters and experimental set-up for optical bleaching of samples and exposure of samples to
287 gamma doses are presented in the supplementary.

288 In addition, we constructed a dose response curve for Al-hole centre for three selected samples
289 (F-01, K-03 and N5) irradiated with 10 different gamma doses ranging from 100-40000 Gy to

290 ascertain the saturation characteristics of the Al-hole centre. Following which we evaluated the
291 intensity of the Al-hole centre for all quartz samples irradiated with a gamma dose of 40000 Gy.

292

293 **4. Results**

294

295 The comparison of single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity from three compositionally different
296 sandstones (N5, K-03 and F-01) with respect to their corresponding U-Pb age distribution on
297 detrital zircons are shown in Figure 2a. Assuming total occupancy of single grain discs, we
298 observe that of the total number of grains ($n_t=2900$) analysed for each sample, only 3% of the
299 grains in sample N5, as compared to c. 7-10% of the grains in Kliwa (K-01, K-02 and K-03) and
300 c.7 % of the grains in Fusaru (F-01) give an OSL sensitivity greater than the defined detection
301 threshold (≥ 22 counts in 0.1s). Of the grains that give a detectable signal, 100% of such grains
302 in sample N5, 92-96% of the grains in Kliwa and 95% of the grains in Fusaru have OSL
303 sensitivities between 22-1000 cts/34Gy·grain. While the remaining 5% of grains in Fusaru and
304 c. 2-5% of the grains in Kliwa's are constrained within OSL sensitivities of 1000-3000
305 cts/34Gy·grain. Lastly, the remaining c.1-2% of the grains in Kliwa have sensitivities >3000-
306 21000 cts/34Gy·grain. Thus, assuming maximum occupancy of the discs ($n_t=2900$ grains), our
307 results suggest that the average bulk luminescence sensitivity of our samples is dominated by c.
308 1% of the total quartz grains, which exhibit individual OSL sensitivity of >1000 cts/34Gy·grain,
309 as seen in the case of Kliwa and Fusaru samples. The classification of the number of individual
310 grains with different OSL sensitivities is tabulated in Table S3.

311

312 Moreover, comparison of single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity distribution patterns with their
313 corresponding U-Pb zircon age distribution shown in Figure 2 shows a distinct difference for
314 samples derived from a single source versus those with multiple sources. For instance, sample
315 N5 with a localised single source exhibits a more constrained behaviour, while samples with
316 contribution from multiple sources such as Fusaru and Kliwa, display a higher scatter in the OSL
317 sensitivity distribution. Finally, it is observed that sample N5, with a predominantly single older
318 source (with U-Pb zircon age peak c. 2082 Ma) and high depositional age (>560 Ma), exhibits
319 the lowest OSL sensitivity as compared to Kliwa and Fusaru samples, which have a lower
320 depositional age (c.19-30 Ma) with contributions from comparatively younger sources with U-
321 Pb zircon age spectrum spanning c. 114 to 3250 Ma and c. 21.3 to 2893 Ma for Kliwa and Fusaru
322 samples respectively.

323
324 Figure 3 presents the results of multi-grain OSL sensitivity analysis conducted by (i) treating
325 single-grain discs as multi-grain aliquot – resulting in ‘pseudo multi-grain aliquots’ (Figure 3a,b)
326 and (ii) conventional multi-grain aliquots stimulated with blue diodes (Figure 3c,d). In the first
327 case, Figure 3a allows us to visualise how the dispersion in OSL sensitivity of individual quartz
328 grains in the sample (as seen in Figure 2) can lead to large uncertainty as observed in the ‘pseudo
329 multi-grain’ OSL sensitivity analysis. In the second case, Figure 3c we conduct conventional
330 OSL sensitivity measurements on multi-grain aliquots under blue stimulation. Here again, we
331 see that Kliwa and Fusaru samples exhibit higher uncertainty compared to sample N5. Our
332 overall analysis of average OSL sensitivity in multi-grain aliquots (Figure 3a and 3c) shows that
333 irrespective of the method of analysis (pseudo and/or conventional), the random uncertainty on
334 Kliwa and Fusaru samples is higher as compared to sample N5. Thus, uncertainty on the average
335 OSL sensitivity in multi-grain aliquots is subject to random variation depending on the
336 occurrence of the ‘number’ and ‘type’ (dim or bright) of grains.

337
338 Figure 4 shows that the intensity of the E'_1 centre of the samples increase with the age of the
339 source rock. Accordingly, sample N5 owing to an older source has the highest E'_1 intensity
340 followed by Kliwa (K-01, K-02 and K-03) and Fusaru (F-01) samples. This observation agrees
341 with previous studies that have shown a correlation between intensity of natural E'_1 centre and
342 age of the granitic source rock (Odom and Rink., 1989; Dave et al., 2022; Timar-Gabor et al.,
343 2023). Previous laboratory-based experiments have shown that the intensity of E'_1 centre
344 increases on heating as the thermally activated electronic holes released by the Al-hole centres
345 are captured by the diamagnetic oxygen deficiency centres to yield a paramagnetic E'_1 centres
346 (Jani et al., 1983; Toyoda and Hattori, 2000; Usami et al., 2009). Thus, we expect that the
347 geochemical composition (Al concentration) and thermal history (temperature) will also dictate
348 the intensity of E'_1 in rocks. However, the extent of such effects as yet remains unexplored.
349 Therefore, intensity of the E'_1 centre in quartz is characteristic of the source rock, depending
350 both on the age and type of rock.

351
352 Measurement of ESR intensity of E'_1 and Al-hole centre in natural, laboratory ‘bleached’ and
353 gamma-irradiated (40000 Gy) quartz from all samples is tabulated in Table 1. We observe that
354 on optical bleaching, the natural E'_1 intensity increases while natural Al-hole centre intensity
355 decreases, such that the increase in E'_1 intensity shows a positive correlation with the decrease
356 in Al-hole centre intensity, with a Pearson coefficient of 0.96 (Table 1, Figure S5). The Al-hole

357 centre intensity of quartz irradiated with a gamma dose of 40000 Gy for all the compositionally
358 different sandstones (N5, Kliwas and Fusaru) yield different values, while all the Kliwa samples
359 give comparable values (Table 1). It must be noted here that for our samples the intensity of the
360 Al-hole centre at c. 40000 Gy lies in the saturation zone of its dose response curve as illustrated
361 in Figure 4. To theoretically validate the saturation of Al-hole centre in quartz, we analyse the
362 slope of the curve at 40000 Gy and assess how any further increase in dose will change the Al-
363 hole centre intensity. Our results suggest that beyond 40000 Gy, any further increase in dose will
364 result in an increase that is less than the uncertainty on the intensity observed at 40000 Gy (i.e.,
365 <0.15 a.u), therefore suggesting that our sample lies in saturation. Also, previous work on
366 reconstructing dose response curves upto 200000 Gy on coarse-grain quartz have shown that Al-
367 hole intensity saturates by c.40000 Gy (Benzid and Timar-Gabor, 2020).

368

369 **5. Discussion**

370

371 *5.1. Single-grain versus multi-grain OSL sensitivity*

372

373 Quartz extracted from sediments within a sedimentary basin is likely to be contributed by
374 different sources in varying amounts. Assuming that quartz from different sources yields
375 different sensitivities, multi-grain (or bulk) quartz luminescence sensitivity analysis is likely to
376 homogenise the differences or skew the results as compared to single-grain analysis. On the other
377 hand, single-grain analysis has the potential to identify and reflect different source contributions
378 in the sediment. Therefore, in this study we illustrate the differences between quartz single and
379 multi-grain luminescence sensitivity measurements and its impact on potential interpretation of
380 provenance by studying compositionally different sandstones that have well-characterised
381 sources based on U-Pb zircon ages.

382

383 Single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity distributions (Figure 2) on sandstones show that sample N5
384 is well-constrained unlike Kliwa (K-01, K-02 and K-03) and Fusaru (F-01) samples that are more
385 scattered. These distributions correspond with the U-Pb zircon age distribution, which suggests
386 that sample N5 is predominantly derived from a single source, as compared to Fusaru and Kliwa
387 samples that contain contributions from multiple sources. However, at the same time previous
388 studies (Roban et al., 2020; Roban et al., 2023) have established that sample N5 had a short and
389 quick transport (c. 10's Km) as compared to Fusaru (c.50-100 Km) and Kliwa (> 400 Km)
390 samples. This raises the question of whether transport distance and consequently long

391 sedimentary histories, played a role in sensitisation of quartz from Kliwa and Fusaru as compared
392 to sample N5. Sedimentary history comprises of processes of (re-) transport, burial and
393 deposition experienced by the grain prior to its deposition in the ultimate sink and has often been
394 associated with increasing the luminescence sensitivity of quartz grains (Pietsch et al., 2008;
395 Jeong and Choi., 2012; Sawakuchi et al., 2011; Mineli et al., 2021). Based on single-grain quartz
396 OSL sensitivity distributions observed in our samples, we hypothesise that transport may aid the
397 inherent ability of quartz grains to sensitise. However, we do not consider it a major factor
398 controlling OSL sensitivity in our samples because if it did, we would expect to see a greater
399 proportion of grains with higher sensitivities in the distribution. For example, a study on
400 luminescence signals from single-grains in loess samples, which are believed to be well
401 transported, also show that more than 70% of the signal was contributed by ~1-2% of the
402 measured grains (Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018). A recent study by Timar-Gabor et al (2023) on
403 loess sediments, observed an increase in OSL sensitivity of loess sediments with crystalline age
404 of the rocks from which they were derived. That said, studies on quartz extracted from rocks of
405 different geological ages and rock types (Sawakuchi et al, 2011; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Guralnik
406 et al, 2015) did not present any conclusive evidence for correlation of OSL sensitivity with rock
407 age, however all these studies observed low sensitivity in metamorphic rocks, especially those
408 heated to more than 380 - 500°C.

409 Another factor that is seldom discussed in sensitivity studies is the phenomenon of charge
410 imbalance in quartz which suggests that high burial doses (c.700 KGy) received during long
411 periods of deposition (in order of millions of years) can lead to desensitisation of quartz (Autzen
412 et al., 2018, 2021). This behaviour of desensitisation was recently modelled by Baly et al (2021)
413 for quartz in rocks with ages that vary between 26-1040 Ma using radiation transport models. In
414 their models, assuming that rock age corresponds to time spent by the rock at the earth's surface
415 at ambient temperature of 20°C and negligible pressure, they show that rocks of younger age
416 (e.g., 26 Ma) do not desensitise, while rocks older than 500 Ma show strong and/or complete
417 desensitisation. This desensitisation behaviour was previously observed, not only in older
418 granitic rocks (c. 1000 Ma; Rink et al, 1994) but also on Silurian (c. 444 Ma) sedimentary units
419 (del Río et al, 2021). Thus, the concept of desensitisation holds true for rocks (assuming ambient
420 temperature and negligible pressure) as well as sediments with long burial histories (e.g.
421 sedimentary rocks). However, the fate of desensitised quartz, i.e., its ability to regain, lose or
422 maintain its sensitivity, post erosion from the bedrock remains unexplored.

423 Hence, at present there is no conclusive relationship between OSL sensitivity with rock age or
424 type and is therefore, likely to be a product of multiple factors including its thermal history,
425 geochemical composition, internal radioactivity, residence time of quartz in the rock,
426 metamorphism and tectonic activity. These factors together are likely to dictate the inherent
427 luminescence properties of the quartz and its potential ability to sensitise. Nonetheless, based on
428 the influence of different factors discussed above, we attribute the OSL sensitivity observed in
429 this study as follows. Sample N5 has a predominantly single palaeoproterozoic source (localised
430 around c. 2078 Ma: Fig. 2a) and a depositional age of >560 Ma, wherein the total burial dose
431 received by the quartz is >1000 KGy (Table S4) - therefore we attribute the negligible to very
432 low sensitivity of quartz grains to the process of desensitisation of quartz owing to long burial
433 periods. In comparison, Kliwa (K-03, K-02 and K-01) has contributions from multiple sources
434 with age ranges between 114-3250 Ma and a depositional age of 19-30 Ma with burial doses of
435 >14-27 KGy, which is reflected in the scatter of quartz single-grain OSL sensitivity data for
436 Kliwa (Figure 2). Here, the effect of depositional age on quartz sensitivity is estimated to be
437 inconsequential (as modelled by Baly et al., 2021), while the likely cause for the presence of
438 grains with higher sensitivity may be the result of varying contribution from different sources
439 with inherently different sensitivities. Lastly, Fusaru (F - 01) has multiple contributions from
440 sources with zircon age range between 21-2893 Ma, wherein the major input is from
441 metamorphic sources in the age range of c. 21-700 Ma (Figure 2a); and the maximum
442 depositional age of the sample is c.22 Ma, which corresponds to a total burial dose of >40 KGy
443 (Table S4). Therefore, again like Kliwa, desensitisation due to depositional age is unlikely in
444 Fusaru samples, however the comparatively higher amount of single-grain quartz with lower
445 OSL sensitivity in Fusaru as compared to Kliwa can be largely attributed to the presence of
446 metamorphic quartz which has low sensitivity.

447 The comparison between single and multi-grain OSL sensitivity of quartz (Figure 2, Figure 3) in
448 this study provides an insight on the importance of considering single-grain OSL sensitivity of
449 quartz in provenance studies, especially in sedimentary samples. Our results show that only 3-
450 10% of the total grains (c. 2900 grains) in our samples give an OSL sensitivity greater than the
451 defined threshold (OSL sensitivity OSL >22 cts/0.1s per grain). While only c.1% of the total
452 grains in our samples, give an OSL sensitivity of > 1000 cts/34Gy·grain which dictates the
453 variation observed in the average OSL sensitivity between the samples, and is consequently used
454 to differentiate the samples. Furthermore, multi-grain OSL sensitivity analyses for our samples
455 (Figure 3) show that Kliwa samples have large uncertainties and that their average values are

456 similar (within error) to Fusaru, while the OSL sensitivity of sample N5 is comparatively lower.
457 These results can therefore only be interpreted to suggest that the low sensitivity of sample N5
458 is a result of desensitisation due to prolonged burial time (>560 Ma) as compared to Kliwa and
459 Fusaru samples (c. 19-30 Ma). However, multi-grain OSL sensitivities are unable to differentiate
460 between Kliwa and Fusaru samples, nor can it distinguish between sediment samples sourced
461 from a single source as opposed to those with contribution from multiple sources.

462

463 *5.2. Single-grain OSL sensitivity combined with ESR characterisation of bulk quartz*

464

465 As discussed previously, single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity measurements can better enable our
466 understanding of factors dictating luminescence sensitivity of sediments as compared to analysis
467 of multi-grain quartz aliquots. Moreover, single-grain quartz analysis can help differentiate
468 between sedimentary samples sourced from a single source versus those from multiple sources.
469 However, in cases where multiple sources exhibit similar sensitivities, it may be challenging to
470 distinguish between the different sediments derived from these sources. This is also illustrated
471 in our study wherein in the absence of known constraints on sources (e.g., U-Pb zircon ages), we
472 would not be able to clearly distinguish between quartz from Fusaru and Kliwa based on single-
473 grain OSL sensitivity distributions. For this purpose, we complement this study by measurement
474 of the intensity of paramagnetic centres, namely E'_1 and the residual Al-hole centre that are
475 commonly applied in provenance studies on quartz (Tissoux et al., 2015; Toyoda et al., 2016;
476 Dave et al., 2022a).

477

478 The intensity of E'_1 centre in natural quartz extracted from sandstones increases with increase in
479 the age of the source rocks from which it is derived (Figure 4), and successfully differentiates
480 between the three compositionally different sandstones. Although, other factors like the presence
481 of metamorphic quartz in Fusaru can influence the intensity of the E'_1 and consequently the
482 ability to differentiate between the different sandstones. In general, correlation between intensity
483 of E'_1 centre and the cumulative age of the source rock seen in our sample is in agreement with
484 previous observations (Odom and Rink, 1989; Dave et al., 2022a), and therefore reaffirms the
485 intensity of E'_1 centre as an indicator for provenance. In addition, the comparable E'_1 intensities
486 for the three Kliwa samples (K-01, K-02 and K-03; Figure 4) supports the reproducibility within
487 samples from the same sandstone sampled across different locations.

488

489 Previous studies have shown that the intensity of the residual (optically non-bleachable) Al-hole
490 centre is sample dependent, i.e., it depends on the source rock from which the quartz is derived
491 and was therefore proposed as an indicator for provenance (Tissoux et al., 2012, 2015). However,
492 recent studies have shown that for a given sample the residual Al-hole centre intensity also
493 depends on the previous accumulated dose (Timar-Gabor et al., 2020). Our measurements on
494 intensity of residual Al-hole centre on optically bleached quartz was able to distinguish between
495 the three compositionally different sandstones (Table 1; Figure S5b). However, the influence of
496 source and/ or previous accumulated dose on the residual Al-hole center intensity cannot be
497 decoupled in our samples, as we have compositionally different sandstones with varying
498 depositional (burial) doses. Fundamentally, it would be better to evaluate a parameter that is
499 dictated by either one of these factors. Therefore, saturated Al-hole centre intensity of a sample,
500 which is predominantly sample dependent provides a better alternative. Dose response curves of
501 the Al-hole centre intensity reaches saturation in our samples at c. 40000 Gy (Figure 4). We
502 observe that saturated Al-hole centre intensity (at 40000 Gy) is able to distinguish between the
503 three compositionally different sandstones (Table 1). In addition, the saturated Al-hole centre
504 intensities are also comparable for all the Kliwa samples (K-01, K-02 and K-03) which supports
505 the reproducibility of the results within samples of the same composition (i.e., the same source).
506
507 Furthermore, investigation on intensities of E'_1 and the residual Al-hole centres in optically
508 bleached quartz shows that the increase in intensity of E'_1 centre correlates with the decrease in
509 intensity of the Al-hole centre and has a Pearson coefficient of 0.96 (Figure S5). This reaffirms
510 the relationship between formation of E'_1 centres and annihilation of Al-hole centres in quartz
511 on optical stimulation, as observed in previous studies (Timar-Gabor et al., 2020; Benzid and
512 Timar-Gabor, 2021).

513
514

515 **6. Conclusion**

516

517 This study investigates single and multi-grain quartz OSL sensitivity and quartz ESR-centres
518 (E'_1 and Al-hole centres) from three compositionally different sandstones with well-characterised
519 sources with the aim of assessing geological controls on trapped charge characteristics of quartz
520 for provenance studies. Our study successfully distinguishes sedimentary rock samples sourced
521 from a single localised source (Yampil sandstone, N5) from those with multiple source
522 contributions (Kliwa and Fusaru sandstones) using single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity

523 distributions. However, due to the similarity in quartz single-grain distribution of OSL sensitivity
524 for Kliwa and Fusaru samples, we use the intensity of E'₁ centre in quartz – which is believed to
525 depend on the age of the source rock - to further distinguish between two compositionally
526 different sandstones. Thus, our comparison of results from single versus multi-grain quartz OSL
527 sensitivity studies shows that single-grain quartz analysis in provenance studies offers the
528 advantage of: (i) distinguishing between sediments with single and multiple source contributions,
529 given that there is heterogeneity in luminescence sensitivity in the source signature; while, multi-
530 grain quartz analysis is likely to mask that effect and, (ii) providing a nuanced insight into factors,
531 such as the phenomenon of desensitisation, metamorphism, sediment-transport processes, etc
532 that influence the inherent sensitivity of quartz grains in a sedimentary system. That said,
533 similarity in luminescence sensitivity in the source(s) signatures can result in visually similar
534 single-grain quartz OSL sensitivity distribution patterns that cannot distinguish between
535 compositionally different samples from such sources. In such cases, provenance determining
536 quartz ESR centres, such as E'₁ and saturated Al-hole centre can provide a promising tool to
537 differentiate such samples.

538

539 **Data Availability**

540 The data generated for this study is freely available on zenodo with the doi:

541

542 **Acknowledgements**

543 This study is funded by the European Research Council Consolidator Grant - PROGRESS,
544 (ERC-CoG-101043356). This work is also supported by grants from the Romanian Executive
545 Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation, UEFISCDI: PN-III-P4-
546 PCE-2021-0901 awarded to R.D.R. The views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the
547 authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European
548 Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible
549 for them.

550

551

552

553
 554 **Figure 1.** Regional setting and location of samples analysed in this study. The topographic map
 555 was created using GeoMapApp (<https://www.geomapapp.org>).

556
 557
 558
 559
 560
 561
 562

563

564

565 **Figure 2. (a)** Comparison of U-Pb zircon age distributions (represented as kernel density
 566 estimates; Roban et al., 2020, 2023) with single grain quartz OSL sensitivity distribution on
 567 samples from Yampil (N5), Kliwa (K-02) and Fusaru (F-01) sandstones. **(b)** Single grain quartz
 568 OSL sensitivity distribution on Kliwa samples. The similarity in distribution between the Kliwa
 569 samples assures us of reproducibility in our measurements. *Note:* Histograms for single grain
 570 quartz OSL sensitivity distributions have a bin size of 100 counts. The first bin in each histogram
 571 has values between 22-100 counts, as 22 counts was defined as the detection threshold for our
 572 samples.

573

574

(i) Pseudo multi-grain luminescence sensitivity analysis

(ii) Conventional multi-grain luminescence sensitivity analysis

575
576 **Figure 3.** Plot of multi-grain quartz OSL sensitivity of sandstone samples (a, b) and its
577 corresponding dose response curve (c,d) reconstructed using a twofold approach (i) ‘Pseudo’
578 multi-grain luminescence sensitivity analysis – which is evaluated by treating each single grain
579 disc as a multi-grain aliquot (i.e., by summing the grains on each disc) and (ii) Conventional
580 multi-grain OSL sensitivity evaluated from 9 multi-grain aliquots stimulated with blue light.
581 Here n_e/n_t refers to the number of aliquots used to calculate OSL sensitivity versus the total
582 number of aliquots analysed. The average dose response curves from all the analysed aliquots
583 were fitted using a sum of two exponentials, which gave the best fit for all samples. The
584 uncertainties on the average OSL sensitivity in plot 3a and 3c represent standard errors of the
585 mean and represent 1σ .

586
587
588
589

590
 591 **Figure 4. (a)** Intensity of E₁' centre in natural quartz from sandstones. The samples (from left to
 592 right) are arranged in order of increasing crystalline age of source rocks from which it is derived.
 593 The intensities represent an average of 3 measurements that is normalised to 100 mg. The
 594 reported uncertainties are standard error of the mean and represent 1 σ . **(b)** Dose response curves
 595 for Al-hole centres for samples F-01, K-03 and N5 in response to laboratory gamma irradiation.

596
 597
 598
 599
 600
 601
 602
 603
 604
 605
 606
 607
 608
 609
 610
 611
 612
 613

614 **Table. 1.** Intensity of paramagnetic centres E'_1 and $[AlO_4]^0$ in natural (as obtained on extraction
615 from sediment), bleached (for 75 days in the laboratory) and gamma (γ)-irradiated (40000 Gy)
616 quartz from all samples. For comparison, the intensities (in arbitrary units) have been normalised
617 to 100 mg for all samples. The reported uncertainties are the standard error of the mean and
618 represent 1σ .

619

620

Stratigraphic unit	Sample	ESR intensities normalised to 100 mg				
		Natural Quartz		Bleached Quartz		γ -Irradiated (40,000 Gy) Quartz
		E'_1	$[AlO_4]^0$	Bleached E'_1	Residual $[AlO_4]^0$	$[AlO_4]^0$
<i>Yampil Member</i>	N5	0.107 ± 0.001	4.68 ± 0.05	0.655 ± 0.015	3.55 ± 0.04	5.36 ± 0.15
<i>Lower Kliwa Formation</i>	K-03	0.070 ± 0.001	1.69 ± 0.03	0.342 ± 0.001	1.02 ± 0.03	3.36 ± 0.02
	K-02	0.071 ± 0.000	1.40 ± 0.05	0.345 ± 0.023	0.80 ± 0.00	3.74 ± 0.04
<i>Upper Kliwa Formation</i>	K-01	0.068 ± 0.001	1.34 ± 0.01	0.309 ± 0.021	0.87 ± 0.03	4.83 ± 0.09
<i>Fusaru Formation</i>	F-01	0.016 ± 0.001	0.56 ± 0.01	0.056 ± 0.007	0.20 ± 0.01	2.66 ± 0.01

621

622

623

624

625

626

627 **References:**

628

629 Ackerson, M. R., N. D. Tailby, and E. B. Watson (2015), Trace elements in quartz shed light on
630 sediment provenance, *Geochem. Geophys. Geosyst.*, 16, 1894–1904,
631 doi:[10.1002/2015GC005896](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GC005896).

632

633 Alexanderson, H. 2022. Luminescence characteristics of Scandinavian quartz, their connection
634 to bedrock provenance and influence on dating results. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 69,
635 101-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2022.101272>.

636

637 Allen, P. From landscapes into geological history. *Nature* 451, 274–276 (2008).
638 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06586>

639

640 Anechitei-Deacu, V., Timar-Gabor, A., Thomsen, K.J., Buylaert, J.-P., Jain, M., Bailey, M.,
641 Murray, A.S. 2018. Single and multi-grain OSL investigations in the high dose range using
642 coarse quartz. *Radiation Measurements*, 120, 124-130.
643 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.06.008>.

644

645 Autzen, M., Murray, A.S., Guérin, G., Baly, L., Ankjærgaard, C., Bailey, M., Jain, M.,
646 Buylaert, J.-P. 2018. Luminescence dosimetry: Does charge imbalance matter? *Radiation*
647 *Measurements* 120, 26-32.

648

649 Autzen, M., Murray, A.S., Jain, M., Buylaert, J-P. 2021. Further investigations into the effect of
650 charge imbalance on luminescence production. *Journal of Luminescence*, 238, 118223.
651 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlumin.2021.118223>.

652

653 Baly, L., Quesada, I., Murray, A.S., Martin, G., Espen, P., Arteché, R., Jain, M. 2021. Modeling
654 the charge deposition in quartz grains during natural irradiation and its influence on the
655 optically stimulated luminescence signal. *Radiation Measurements*, 142, 106564.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106564>.

657

658 Beerten, K., Pierreux, D., Stesmans, A. 2003. Towards single grain ESR dating of sedimentary
659 quartz: first results. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 22 (10–13), 1329-1334.
660 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(03\)00060-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(03)00060-X).

661
662 Benzid, K., Timar-Gabor, A. 2020. Phenomenological model of aluminium-hole ($[AlO_4/h^+]_0$)
663 defect formation in sedimentary quartz upon room temperature irradiation: electron spin
664 resonance (ESR) study. *Radiation Measurements* (130), 106187.
665 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2019.106187>.
666
667 Benzid, K., Timar-Gabor, A. 2021. On the dose dependence prior and after stimulation with
668 visible light of E' and Al-hole centres in sedimentary quartz: Correlation and mechanisms.
669 *Radiation Measurements*, 141, 106522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106522>.
670
671 Bartyik, T., Magyar, G., Filyó, D., Tóth, O., Blanka-Végi, V., Kiss, T., Marković, S., Persoiu, I.,
672 Gavrilov, M., Mezősi, G., Sipos, G. 2021. Spatial differences in the luminescence
673 sensitivity of quartz extracted from Carpathian Basin fluvial sediments. *Quaternary*
674 *Geochronology*, 64, 101-166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2021.101166>
675
676 Basu, A. (1985). Reading Provenance from Detrital Quartz. In: Zuffa, G.G. (eds) *Provenance*
677 *of Arenites*. NATO ASI Series, vol 148. Springer, Dordrecht. [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-2809-6_11)
678 [94-017-2809-6_11](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-2809-6_11)
679
680 Capaldi, T.N., Rittenour, T.M., Nelson, M.S. 2022. Downstream changes in quartz OSL
681 sensitivity in modern river sand reflects sediment source variability: Case studies from
682 Rocky Mountain and Andean rivers. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 71, 101317.
683 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2022.101317>.
684
685 Dave, A. K., Timar-Gabor, A., Kabacińska, Z., Scardia, G., Safaraliev, N., Nigmatova, S., &
686 Fitzsimmons, K. E. 2022a. A novel proxy for tracking the provenance of dust based on
687 paired E1'-peroxy paramagnetic defect centers in fine-grained quartz. *Geophysical*
688 *Research Letters*, 49, e2021GL095007. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL095007>
689 Dave, A.K, Timar-Gabor, A., Scardia, G., Safaraliev, N., Fitzsimmons, K.E. 2022b. Variation in
690 Luminescence Characteristics and Paramagnetic Defect Centres in Fine-Grained Quartz
691 From a Loess-Palaeosol Sequence in Tajikistan: Implications for Provenance Studies in
692 Aeolian Environments. *Frontiers in Earth Science*. 10:835281. doi:
693 10.3389/feart.2022.835281. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2022.835281>
694

695 del Río, I., Sawakuchi, A. O., Góes, A. M., Hollanda, M. H. B. M., Furukawa, L. Y., Porat,
696 N., Jain, M., Mineli, T. D., & Negri, F. D. A. (2021). Luminescence signals of quartz and
697 feldspar as new methods for stratigraphic discrimination and provenance analysis of
698 siliciclastic successions: The case of the Parnaíba Basin (Brazil) of West Gondwana. *Basin*
699 *Research*, 33, 2938–2959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bre.12590>
700

701 Duller, G.A.T., Bøtter-Jensen, L., Murray, A.S. 2000. Optical dating of single sand-sized grains
702 of quartz: sources of variability. *Radiation Measurements*, 32 (5–6), 453-457.
703 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(00\)00055-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(00)00055-X).
704

705 Feigl, F. J., Fowler, W. B., & Yip, K. L. (1974). Oxygen vacancy model for the E1' center in
706 SiO₂. *Solid State Communications*, 14(3), 225–229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1098(74)90840-0)
707 [1098\(74\)90840-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1098(74)90840-0)
708

709 Francovschi, I., Grădinaru, E., Li, H., Shumlyanskyy, L. & Ciobotaru, V. (2021). U–Pb
710 Geochronology and Hf Isotope Systematics of Detrital Zircon from the Late Ediacaran
711 Kalyus Beds (East European Platform): Palaeogeographic Evolution of Southwestern
712 Baltica and Constraints on the Ediacaran Biota. *Precambrian Research*, 355, 106062. doi:
713 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2020.106062>.
714

715 Francovschi I., Shumlyanskyy L., Soesoo A., Tarasko I., Melnychuk V., Hoffmann A.,
716 Kovalick A., Love G., & Bekker A., (2023). U–Pb geochronology of detrital zircon from
717 the Ediacaran and Cambrian sedimentary successions of NE Estonia and Volyn region of
718 Ukraine: Implications for the provenance and comparison with other areas within Baltica,
719 *Precambrian Research*, **392**, 107087, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2023.107087>.
720

721 Guralnik, B., Ankjaergaard, C., Jain, M., Murray, A.S., Müller, A., Wälle, M., Lowick, S.E.,
722 Preusser, F., Rhodes, E.J., Wu, T.-S., Mathew, G., Herman, F. 2015a. OSL609
723 thermochronometry using bedrock quartz: A note of caution. *Quaternary Geochronology*
724 *25* (610), 37-48.
725

726 Jani, M. G., Bossoli, R. B., & Halliburton, L. E. (1983). Further characterization of the E1' center in
727 crystalline SiO₂. *Physical Review B*, 27(4), 2285–2293. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.27.2285>
728

729 Jeong, G. Y., and Choi, J.-H. (2012). Variations in Quartz OSL Components with Lithology,
730 Weathering and Transportation. *Quat. Geochronol.* 10, 320–326.
731 doi:10.1016/j.quageo.2012.02.023
732

733 Mineli, T. D., Sawakuchi, A. O., Guralnik, B., Lambert, R., Jain, M., Pupim, F. N., Rio, I. D.,
734 Guedes, C. C. F., & Nogueira, L. (2021). Variation of luminescence sensitivity,
735 characteristic dose and trap parameters of quartz from rocks and sediments. *Radiation*
736 *Measurements*, 144, [106583]. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106583>
737

738 Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2000. Luminescence dating of quartz using an improved single
739 aliquot regenerative-dose protocol. *Radiation Measurements* 32, 57-73.
740

741 Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2003. The single aliquot regenerative dose protocol: potential for
742 improvements in reliability. *Radiation Measurements*, 37 (4-5), 377-381.
743 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(03)00053-2).

744 Melinte, C.M. (2005). Oligocene Palaeoenvironmental Changes in the Romanian Carpathians,
745 Revealed by Calcareous Nannofossils. *Studia Geologica Polonica*, **124**, 341-352.
746

747 Nagashima, K., Tada, R., Tani, A., Toyoda, S., Sun, Y., and Isozaki, Y. (2007). Contribution of
748 Aeolian Dust in Japan Sea Sediments Estimated from ESR Signal Intensity and
749 Crystallinity of Quartz. *Geochem. Geophys. Geosyst.* 8 (2), a–n.
750 doi:10.1029/2006GC001364
751

752 Nagashima, K., Tada, R., Tani, A., Sun, Y., Isozaki, Y., Toyoda, S., et al. (2011). Millennial-
753 scale Oscillations of the Westerly Jet Path during the Last Glacial Period. *J. Asian Earth*
754 *Sci.* 40 (6), 1214–1220. doi:10.1016/j.jseaes.2010.08.010
755

756 Odom, A.L., Rink, W. J., 1989. Natural accumulation of Schottky-Frenkel defects;
757 Implications for a quartz geochronometer. *Geology* 17, 55-58.
758

759 Paszkowski, M., Budzyn, B., Mazur, S., Slama, J., Shumlyansky, L., Srodon, J., Dhuime, B.,
760 Kedzior, A., Liivamagi, S., Piszczowska, A., 2019. Detrital zircon U-Pb and Hf constraints
761 on provenance and timing of deposition of the Mesoproterozoic to Cambrian sedimentary

762 cover of the East European Craton. Belarus. *Precam. Res.* 331, 1–19.
763 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2019.105352>
764

765 Pietsch, T.J., Olley, J.M., Nanson, G.C., 2008. Fluvial transport as a natural luminescence
766 sensitiser of quartz. *Quaternary Geochronology* 3, 365-376.
767

768 Răbagia, T., Roban, R.D. & Tărăpoancă, M. (2011). Sedimentary Records of Paleogene
769 (Eocene to Lowermost Miocene) Deformations near the Contact between the Carpathian
770 Thrust Belt and Moesia. *Oil Gas Sci. Technol. – Rev. IFP Energies nouvelles*, **66**, 931-
771 952. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2516/ogst/2011146>
772

773 Rink, W.J. 1994. Billion-year age dependence of luminescence in granitic quartz. *Radiation*
774 *Measurements*, 23 (2-3), 419-422. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-4487\(94\)90074-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-4487(94)90074-4).
775

776 Roban, R.D., Ducea, M.N., Mațenco, L., Panaiotu, G.C., Profeta, L., Krézsek, C., Melinte-
777 Dobrinescu, M.C., Anastasiu, N., Dimofte, D., Apotrosoaei, V. & Francovschi, I. 2020.
778 Lower Cretaceous Provenance and Sedimentary Deposition in the Eastern Carpathians:
779 Inferences for the Evolution of the Subducted Oceanic Domain and Its European Passive
780 Continental Margin. *Tectonics*, **39**, e2019TC005780. doi:
781 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019TC005780>.
782

783 Roban, R. D., Ducea, M. N., Mihalcea, V. I., Munteanu, I., Barbu, V., Melinte-Dobrinescu, M.
784 C., Olariu, C., & Vlăsceanu, M. 2023. Provenance of Oligocene lithic and quartz arenites
785 of the East Carpathians: Understanding sediment routing systems on compressional basin
786 margins. *Basin Research*, 35, 244–270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bre.12711>
787

788 Sawakuchi, A.O., Blair, M.W., DeWitt, R., Faleiros, F.M., Hyppolito, T., Guedes, C.C.F.,
789 2011. Thermal history versus sedimentary history: OSL sensitivity of quartz grains
790 extracted from rocks and sediments. *Quaternary Geochronology* 6, 261–272.
791

792 Sawakuchi, A. O., Jain, M., Mineli, T. D., Nogueira, L., Bertassoli, D. J. Jr, Häggi, C.,
793 Sawakuchi, H. O., Pupim, F. N., Grohmann, C. H., Chiessi, C. M., Zabel, M., Mulitza, S.,
794 Mazoca, C. E. M., & Cunha, D. F. (2018). Luminescence of quartz and feldspar
795 fingerprints provenance and correlates with the source area denudation in the Amazon

796 River basin. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 492, 152–162.
797 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EPSL.2018.04.006>
798

799 Shimada, A., Takada, M., and Toyoda, S. (2013). Characteristics of ESR Signals and TLCLs of
800 Quartz Included in Various Source Rocks and Sediments in Japan: A Clue to Sediment
801 Provenance. *Geochronometria* 40 (4), 334–340. doi:10.2478/s13386-013-0111-z
802

803 Ștefănescu, M., Popescu, I., Melinte, M., Ivan, V., Ștefănescu, M., Papaianopol, I., Popescu, G.,
804 & Dumitrică, P. (2018). Harta Geologică a României, Scara 1: 50 000, Foaia 112d, L-35-
805 89-D. Nehoiu.
806

807 Soldatenko, Y., El Albani, A., Ruzina, M., Fontaine, C., Nesterovsky, V., Paquette, J.-L.,
808 Meunier, A., Ovtcharova, M., 2019. Precise U-Pb age constrains on the Ediacaran biota in
809 Podolia, East European Platform, Ukraine. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 1–13.
810 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-38448-9>.
811

812 Souza, P.E., Pupim, F.N., Mazoca, C.E.M., del Río, I., Mineli, T.D., Rodrigues, F.C.G., Porat,
813 N., Hartmann, G.A., Sawakuchi, A.O. 2023. Quartz OSL sensitivity from dating data for
814 provenance analysis of pleistocene and holocene fluvial sediments from lowland
815 Amazonia. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 74, 101422.
816 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2023.101422>.
817

818 Timar-Gabor, A., Chruścińska, A., Benzid, K., Fitzsimmons, K.E., Begy, R., Bailey, M. 2020.
819 Bleaching studies on Al-hole ([AlO₄/h]0) electron spin resonance (ESR) signal in
820 sedimentary quartz. *Radiation Measurements*, 130, 106221.
821 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2019.106221>.
822

823 Timar-Gabor, A., Kabacińska, Z., Constantin, D., Dave, A.K., Buylaert, J-P. 2023.
824 Reconstructing dust provenance from quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and
825 electron spin resonance (ESR) signals: Preliminary results on loess from around the world.
826 *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 212, 111138.
827 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2023.111138>.
828

829 Tissoux, H., Voinchet, P., Lacquement, F., Prognon, F., Moreno, D., Falguères, C., Bahain, J.-J.,
830 Toyoda, S. 2012. Investigation on non-optically bleachable components of ESR aluminium
831 signal in quartz. *Radiation Measurements*, 47(9), 894-899.
832 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2012.03.012>.
833

834 Tissoux, H., Voinchet, P., Lacquement, F., and Despriée, F. (2015). ESR as a Method for the
835 Characterization of Alluvial Sediments. *Radiat. Meas.* 81, 2–8.
836 doi:10.1016/j.radmeas.2015.05.010
837

838 Toyoda, S., and Hattori, W. 2000. Formation and Decay of the E1' Center and of its Precursor.
839 *Applied Radiation Isotopes* 52 (5), 1351–1356. doi:10.1016/S0969-8043(00)00094-4
840

841 Toyoda, S., Nagashima, K., and Yamamoto, Y. (2016). ESR Signals in Quartz: Applications to
842 Provenance Research - A Review. *Quaternary International*, 397, 258–266.
843 doi:10.1016/j.quaint.2015.05.048
844

845 Usami, T., Toyoda, S., Bahadur, H., Srivastava, A.K., Nishido, H. 2009. Characterization of the
846 E1' center in quartz: Role of aluminum hole centers and oxygen vacancies, *Physica B:
847 Condensed Matter*, 404 (20), 3819-3823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2009.07.075>.
848

849 Weltje, G.J., von Eynatten, H. 2004. Quantitative provenance analysis of sediments: review and
850 outlook. *Sedimentary Geology*, 171(1–4), 1-11.
851 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2004.05.007>.
852
853
854
855
856
857
858
859
860